

Studies on Ti/Al sheet joint using Laser beam welding - A Review

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Abstract : Laser beam welding has wide acceptability due to least welding distortion, low labour costs and convenient operation. However laser welding for dissimilar Titanium and Aluminium alloys is a new area which is having wider applications in aerospace, aircraft, automotive, electronics and other industries. The present study is concerned with welding parameters namely laser power, welding speed, focusing distance and type of shielding gas and thereby evaluate welding performance of Titanium and Aluminium alloy thin sheets. This paper reviews the basic concepts associated with different parameters of Ti/Al sheet joint using Laser beam welding.

Keywords : Laser Beam Welding (LBW), Dissimilar joining Titanium and Aluminum sheets.

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